

Polarographic Study of Mixed-ligand Complexes. Indium(III)—L-Glutamate—L-Methioninate/ L-Valinate/L-Proline Systems

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The mixed-ligand complexes of In^{3+} with L-glutamate and L-methionine/L-valine/L-proline have been investigated by polarographic technique. The cathodic reduction of mixed complexes involved three electrons, reversible and diffusion-controlled step. The logarithmic values of overall formation constants of $\text{In}(\text{L-glutamate})(\text{L-methioninate})$, $\text{In}(\text{L-glutamate})(\text{L-valinate})$ and $\text{In}(\text{L-glutamate})(\text{L-proline})$ complexes were 16.78, 17.19 and 18.00, respectively. The positive values of logarithm of mixing constant revealed that the mixed complexes were more stable than the parent bis-complexes.

RECENTLY equilibrium study of mixed-ligand complexes of In^{3+} has been undertaken by various workers¹⁻⁶. However, stability constants of mixed-ligand complex species of In^{3+} with amino acids have not been determined previously. The author has employed polarographic technique to evaluate the stability constants of mixed-amino-acid complexes of In^{3+} ⁷⁻¹⁰. It had been generally observed that the stability constants of mixed-ligand complexes of In^{3+} with bidentate amino acids were nearly equal to the average of stabilities of bis-complexes of the ligands⁸⁻¹⁰. However, the stability of the mixed-ligand complex $\text{In}(\text{L-glutamate})(\text{L-leucinate})$ was found higher than statistically expected value⁷. This exceptional behaviour was considered to be due to the tridentate nature of glutamate ion which yielded a neutral mixed-ligand complex species. Further investigations were necessary to understand clearly the role of glutamate ion in the mixed-ligand complexes of In^{3+} . The present communication therefore deals with the polarographic study of In^{3+} -L-glutamate-L-methioninate/L-valinate/L-proline systems.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of reagent grade. The ligands, L-methionine and L-glutamic acids were B.D.H. (England) products while L-valine and L-proline Sigma products. The solution of L-glutamic acid was prepared by dissolving it in dilute perchloric acid due to its low solubility in water. Solution of indium nitrate (Schuchardt Munchen) was prepared in dilute perchloric acid and was standardised against EDTA using PAN indicator¹¹. The pH of test solutions were adjusted by adding requisite amount of perchloric acid or CO_2 -free sodium hydroxide solution. Triton X-100 was

added to suppress the maximum in the In^{3+} -L-glutamate-L-methioninate system. Pure nitrogen was used to deaerate the solutions.

Polarograms were obtained at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with the help of a Toshniwal polarograph. The dropping mercury electrode had capillary characteristic (*vs* SCE) $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.261 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$.

Results and Discussion

Reversible and diffusion controlled waves of In^{3+} were obtained in the presence and absence of ligands. The half-wave potential of In^{3+} at pH 3.0–3.3 was -0.512 V vs SCE in 0.1 M sodium perchlorate. The simple systems, In^{3+} -L-glutamate, In^{3+} -L-methioninate, In^{3+} -L-valinate and In^{3+} -L-proline have already been studied^{7,8,10}.

Mixed-ligand systems: The systems In^{3+} -L-glutamate-L-valinate and In^{3+} -L-glutamate-L-proline were investigated by keeping the concentration of glutamate ion constant and varying the concentrations of L-valinate or L-proline ion, respectively. The concentration of In^{3+} used in these systems was $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$. However, in the system In^{3+} -L-glutamate-L-methioninate, the concentration of L-methioninate ion was kept constant while that of L-glutamate ion was changed. In this case, the concentration of In^{3+} was kept low ($1.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) due to the low solubility of L-glutamic acid.

The log plot analyses indicated that all the systems behaved reversibly (slope $21 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$). The limiting currents of all the polarograms were found to be diffusion-controlled. The half-wave potentials shifted towards more negative potentials on increasing the concentration of the variable ligand (X) at a fixed concentration of the other ligand (Y).

These shifts ($E_{1/2}$) were found to be greater than that observed with the simple $\text{In}^{III}-\text{X}$ system.

The free ligand concentration of the ligands were calculated from pK values at 30° which were obtained by putting the reported values of pK^{12-15} and $-\Delta H^{15,16}$ at 25° .

The plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log(X)$ yielded smooth curves suggesting the existence of more than one complex species in solution. Hence, Schaap and McMasters technique¹⁷ was employed to evaluate the overall stability constants of mixed complex species, whose method of calculation has been described earlier^{7,8}. The values of A , B , C and $\log C$ obtained for different mixed systems are reported in Table 1.

nearly equal for all the systems. Hence, the values of $\log K_s$ are positive for all the mixed complex species.

The results clearly indicate that the mixed complex species of In^{III} with the L-glutamate and L-methioninate/L-valinate/L-leucinate/L-prolinate are more stable than the simple bis-complexes. These neutral mixed complex species are formed due to the tridentate nature of glutamate ion. It has been concluded by several workers^{17,19-22} that the extra stabilisation is considerably large in cases where the formation of a mixed complex involves neutralisation of charge (i.e. when the mixed species is neutral while the binary species are charged). This suggests that the formation of the above stable

TABLE 1—MIXED STABILITY CONSTANT PARAMETERS AT 30° AND $\mu = 0.1$ (NaClO_4)

Variable ligand	Fixed ligand	Concentration of fixed ligand M	A^a	B^a	C^a	$\log C^a$
L-Glutamate	L-Methioninate	1.00×10^{-7}	3.96	7.238×10^9	1.168×10^{15}	18.07
L-Glutamate	L-Methioninate	2.87×10^{-7}	22.32	1.551×10^{10}	1.095×10^{16}	18.04
L-Valinate	L-Glutamate	5.64×10^{-8}	26.14	1.005×10^9	3.883×10^{16}	15.59
L-Valinate	L-Glutamate	8.56×10^{-8}	57.10	1.080×10^9	3.543×10^{16}	15.55
L-Glutamate	L-Leucinate	1.39×10^{-8}	1.98	3.604×10^7	1.299×10^{16}	18.11
L-Glutamate	L-Leucinate	4.01×10^{-8}	7.14	7.801×10^7	9.763×10^{17}	17.99
L-Prolinate	L-Glutamate	2.86×10^{-8}	8.04	3.248×10^7	1.033×10^{17}	17.01
L-Prolinate	L-Glutamate	3.76×10^{-8}	12.69	3.506×10^8	8.365×10^{16}	16.92

^a Ref. 17.

Comparison of stability of complexes: It has been reported earlier¹⁸ that the stability of the ternary (mixed) complexes increases with the basicity of the structurally related ligands. The results (Table 2) observed also suggest that the stability of the mixed-ligand complexes $\text{In}(\text{L-glutamate})(\text{L}_1)$ (where, $\text{L}_1 = \text{L-methioninate, L-valinate, L-leucinate or L-prolinate}$) increases with the increase in basicity. The stability of the mixed-ligand complex can be compared with binary complexes through $K_m^{7,8}$. The log of stabilisation constant, $\log K_s (= \log K_m - 0.3)$, measures the extra stability of the mixed complex, due to electrostatic forces,

$\log K_m^*$ (0.52 ± 0.06) are mixed complex species is due to the enthalpy (coulombic effect) and positive entropy (desolvation of the charged species) effects.

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References

1. Y. D. FRIDMAN, R. I. SOROCHEN and N. V. DOLGASHOVA, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1962, 7, 2127.
2. M. SUNDARESAN and A. K. SUNDARAM, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1975, 82, 77.
3. A. J. AGA and R. M. SATHE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 860.
4. S. D. ERSHOVA, A. YA. FRIDMAN, N. M. DYATLOVA, B. V. ZHANDOV and I. A. POLYAKOVA, *Koord. Khim.*, 1978, 4, 182 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, 88, 127146).
5. S. D. ERSHOVA, A. YA. FRIDMAN and N. M. DYATLOVA, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1974, 24, 514 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, 90, 142759).
6. A. YA. FRIDMAN, S. D. ERSHOVA and N. M. DYATLOVA, *Koord. Khim.*, 1978, 4, 1849 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, 90, 77253).
7. S. L. JAIN and R. C. KAPOOR, *Proc. Natl. Sci. Acad., India, Sect. A*, 1980, 46, 53.
8. S. L. JAIN and R. C. KAPOOR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 351.
9. J. KISHAN, S. L. JAIN and A. PRAKASH, *Proceedings 67th Indian Science Congress, Pt. III, Abstracts*, 1980, p. 50.
10. S. L. JAIN, Ph.D. Thesis, Jodhpur University, 1981.

TABLE 2—COMPLEX FORMATION CONSTANTS FOR MIXED-LIGAND COMPLEXES AT 30° AND $\mu = 0.1$ (NaClO_4)

Compd.	$\log \beta_{1nX}$	$\log K_m$	$\log K_m^*$	$\log K_s$
$\text{In}(\text{L-glutamate})\text{-(L-methioninate)}$	16.78	0.66	0.56	0.36
$\text{In}(\text{L-glutamate})\text{-(L-valinate)}$	17.19	0.44	0.47	0.14
$\text{In}(\text{L-glutamate})\text{-(L-leucinate)}$	17.32	0.64	0.54	0.34
$\text{In}(\text{L-glutamate})\text{-(L-prolinate)}$	18.00	0.57	0.58	0.27

steric factor, solvent etc. The values of $\log K_m^*$ and $\log K_s$ have been reported in Table 2. The values of $\log K_m^*$ have been calculated by using the values of $\log C$ in place of $\log \beta_{1nX}$, and $\log \beta_{1nX}$. The values of $\log K_m$ (0.55 ± 0.11) and

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11. F. J. WELCHER, "The Analytical Uses of EDTA", van Nostrand, Princeton, 1958.
12. M. ISRAELI and L. D. PETTIT, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, 37, 999.
13. R. V. SNYDER and R. J. ANGELICI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, 35, 523.
14. R. J. F. NIVARD and G. I. TESSER in " omprehensive Biochemistry", ed. M. FLORKIN abd E. H. STOTZ, Elsevier, 1965.
15. I. NAGYPAL, A. GERGELY and E. FARKAS, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, 36, 699.
16. J. J. CHRISTENSEN, R. M. IZATT, D. P. WRATHALL and L. D. HANSEN, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1969, 1212.
17. W. B. SCHAAP and D. L. MCMASTERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4699.
18. H. SIGEL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, 37, 507.
19. Y. MARCUS and I. ELIEZER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, 4, 273.
20. W. E. BENNETT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 1291.
21. G. F. CONDIKE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, 31, 2455.
22. H. SIGEL, P. R. HUBER¹ and R. F. PASTERNAK, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, 10, 226.